

TYPES OF SINGLE PERSONS AND THEIR SUBJECTIVE SITUATIONS

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Abstract. *In this article, it is presented that the experience of the feeling of loneliness acquires a special appearance specific to the types, and the subjective states of the information are freely expressed.*

Keywords: *hopeless loneliness, temporary loneliness, passive and stable loneliness, schizophrenia, autism, psychological isolation.*

Loneliness is one of the least scientifically studied social concepts. Demographic data includes statistics on the absolute number and specific gravity of single people. Thus, in a number of developed countries of the world (Holland, Belgium, etc.), single people make up about 30% of the population. Today, one out of every 12 people in the world is experiencing loneliness.

In research, the following types are distinguished among singles. The first type is "desperately lonely", they are not completely satisfied with the relationships of those around them. That's why they don't have a spouse. They rarely made contact with anyone (for example, neighbors). They are characterized by dissatisfaction with their relationships with peers, depression, and a high feeling of abandonment.

Compared to others, they tend to blame other people for their loneliness. Most of the divorced men and women are included in this group.

The second type is "occasionally or temporarily alone". They have enough contact with their friends and acquaintances, even if they do not have close love or are single. They socialize in different places more often than others. Compared to other singles, they are considered socially active. These people see their loneliness as temporary and feel less abandoned than other singles. Among them are the majority of men and women who have never married.

The third type is "passive and stable single". Although they do not have intimate partners and other relationships, they do not complain about it like the first and second types of respondents. These are people who have given up their position and accept it as an inevitable possibility. Most of them are divorced people.

Increasing marriage and family dynamics (first of all, nuclearization of families and increasing number of divorces), alienation in big cities, increasing principles of individualism - all these factors primarily affect the increase in the scale of loneliness. In addition, with the increase of loneliness, negative socio-medical factors are mental diseases (schizophrenia), the increase of severe mental states, the spread of autism, the emergence of painful communication as a result of gross mistakes in obstetrics and negative consequences of education.

To date, the increase in the number of people living alone in the world and the acceptance of loneliness as an acceptable way of life is the reason for the formation of a specific service sector for this category of the population. It was found that as single people have more opportunity and desire to spend more money on their hobbies, tourism and leisure, they buy more expensive products, mainly for sports and tourism as long as they can. In addition, special residential complexes are being built mainly for people without families abroad, and any of their needs are

being met in the service market. It should not be forgotten that this applies only to people who are conscious and comfortable with loneliness and do not feel the need for family ties.

The prevalence of loneliness among people (especially in European countries) is evidenced by the following data: more than 1-2% of respondents stated that they had never experienced loneliness in their lives. About 10-30% said that they experienced such a feeling at least once in their life.

The concept of loneliness is associated with the experience of situations that are subjectively undesirable, perceived as positive intimate relationships with other people. Loneliness is not always accompanied by social isolation of the individual. It is about constantly being among and with people and at the same time feeling psychologically isolated from them (for example, if it is not strangers or people who are strangers to the person).

The level of loneliness experience also does not depend on the number of years a person has spent away from human contact. People who live alone all their lives are sometimes less lonely than those who need to communicate with others. A person who has little contact with others, who does not show the psychological or behavioral reactions of loneliness, cannot be called lonely. In addition, people may not realize that there are discrepancies between actual and desired relationships with others.

True subjective states of loneliness are usually accompanied by symptoms of mental disorder. They take the form of affects with a distinctly negative emotional meaning, and different people have different affective reactions to loneliness. Some lonely people experience sadness and depression, others fear and anxiety, and still others bitterness and anger.

The experience of loneliness is influenced not by the actual relationship, but by the ideal idea of how it should be. A person with a strong need for communication feels lonely if his contacts are limited to one or two people. But he wants to communicate with many people. At the same time, a person who has not experienced such a need may not feel lonely even in the absence of contact with other people.

Loneliness comes with some typical symptoms. Usually, lonely people feel psychologically isolated from other people, incapable of normal interpersonal communication, close interpersonal relationships such as friendship or love with others. A lonely person is one who, among other things, feels depressed, experiencing a lack of communication skills.

A lonely person is different from everyone else and considers himself an unattractive person. He claims that no one likes and respects him. These characteristics of a lonely person's attitude towards himself are often accompanied by specific negative effects, including feelings of anger, sadness and deep unhappiness. A lonely person avoids social contacts and isolates himself from other people without realizing it, and is characterized by paranormality, impulsivity, excessive nervousness, fear, anxiety, weakness and despair.

Lonely people especially do not like outgoing, successful and happy people. This is their protective reaction, which in turn prevents them from building good relationships with people. Some people believe that loneliness is what drives them to abuse alcohol or drugs, even if they don't admit to it.

A lonely person is characterized by special attention to himself, personal problems and inner experiences. It is characterized by increased anxiety and fear of the disastrous consequences of future situations. When communicating with other people, lonely people talk more about

themselves and change the topic of conversation more often than others. Also, they express their opinions without relying on the comments of their interpersonal partners.

Such people are distinguished by their own problems in interpersonal relationships. They are more easily angered than other people, aggressive, criticize others without reason and in many cases try to put psychological pressure on other people. Lonely people often don't trust people, so they hide their thoughts. For this reason, it is easy for them to change their thoughts and they control their actions very strictly.

Lonely people cannot enjoy being in circles and may have difficulties when they need to call someone, agree on something, or solve personal or other issues.

Lonely people with low self-esteem try to please others based on how they perceive and evaluate them. Lonely people have problems or worries, especially when it comes to personal communication, introducing themselves to others, participating in various activities, and being free and open in communication.

Lonely people are more likely than non-loners to see themselves as incompetent and attribute their interpersonal failures to incompetence. Many tasks in relationships increase their anxiety and decrease their activity. Lonely people have a hard time finding solutions to problems that arise in interpersonal relationships.

Studies have shown that loneliness depends on how you treat yourself. For many people, feelings of loneliness are related to low self-esteem. The resulting feeling of loneliness often leads to feelings of inadequacy and worthlessness.

The feeling of loneliness can increase or decrease depending on the dynamic changes in the norms of individual acceptance due to the establishment and intensity of normal interpersonal communication. These types of standards are usually subjective and not clearly defined. At the same time, such standards are relative and are based on past relationships. A slight decrease in the number of friends or human connections in a person who previously had a large number of them can be perceived as an increase in loneliness. Similar changes occur in people who have had almost no contact with anyone before. People with a limited circle of friends (communication with only a few people) can probably be perceived as a decrease in loneliness.

Lonely people often manage to find reasons for their loneliness. They consider it more in character flaws, lack of abilities, unpleasantness than in factors under conscious voluntary control. They believe that it is due to the lack of their own efforts to establish relations, the ineffectiveness of the tools used, etc. It also refers to negative individual characteristics such as strong internal control and shyness, fear of rejection when entering into intimate relationships with someone. Lack of knowledge about how to behave in such situations in order to strengthen interpersonal relations is also cited as the reason.

How a person reacts to loneliness depends on depression or aggression. The increased feeling of submission or, on the contrary, hostility is associated with the real loneliness of a person among people.

Lonely people often feel worthless, incompetent, and ignored, and these self-deprecating feelings are reinforced by increased self-criticism. The relationship between low self-esteem and loneliness can be explained in two ways. First, low self-esteem leads to alienation; secondly, low self-esteem causes the emergence of a significantly complicating attitude in interpersonal communication and is manifested in this behavior.

There are other hypotheses that explain the phenomenon of loneliness based on interpersonal factors. One of them is the inconsistency between the three selves of the individual:

- the way he perceives himself at the moment (real "I");
- what he wants to be (ideal "I");
- how others perceive him (reflection of "I").

Subjective causes of loneliness are more important than objective causes in its occurrence. This is experimentally confirmed. For example, it has been found that many people are not able to correctly assess the attitude of others towards them, because their self-perception does not completely correspond to how people perceive them.

People with low self-esteem expect others to treat them the same way. Such people react more sharply than others to offers and refusals to establish personal relationships with others. At the same time, people with low self-esteem were more hostile toward those who rejected them personally, especially when responding to external surveys and questionnaires. These people are overly sensitive to criticism and see it as a sign of low self-esteem. It turns out that they have a hard time accepting compliments and are insecure about it, so they are very cautious.

In general, low self-esteem causes a complex of psychological problems that prevent the establishment of positive relationships with people around. This is manifested in self-deprecating consciousness and behavior, feelings of inadequacy, etc. It should be noted that long-term loneliness, in turn, can have a negative effect on self-esteem and weaken a person even more. Negative situations in communication increase feelings of loneliness and, as a result, reduce self-esteem. Low self-esteem may pose a greater risk of loneliness than normal self-esteem because low self-esteem ultimately affects a person's sense of self-worth.

One of the causes of loneliness is that a person feels deprived of the relationships he needs, and is unable to find interpersonal communication at the risk of embarrassment and disappointment. Hostility and passivity, possible causes and simultaneous consequences of loneliness, often accompany it. Fear of the negative consequences of taking the initiative to establish interpersonal relationships makes it increasingly difficult for a person to overcome loneliness, and the fear that arose as a result of previous bad experiences helps to create an environment that further strengthens the feeling of loneliness.

In most cases, loneliness occurs for reasons beyond the control of the person. Being single or not getting married, getting divorced or breaking up can be the cause of loneliness. In such cases, it alienates the person from the people who make up his or her usual social circle, resulting in complete or partial emotional and psychological isolation.

It is logical to distinguish three types of lonely relationships: chronic, situational and transient.

Chronic loneliness occurs when a person lives a long time and does not have enough relationships with important people in his life.

Situational loneliness is usually caused by stressful events in a person's life, such as the death of a loved one or the breakup of a close relationship, such as a marriage. After experiencing grief for a short period of time, the result is isolation and loss of identity, and the resulting feeling of loneliness partially or completely overcomes the person.

Transient loneliness represents short-term attacks of loneliness. They disappear completely and without a trace and leave no trace behind.

Childhood emotional distance, such as parental deprivation or lack of secure relationships and parental support, can predispose an individual to loneliness in adulthood. Emotional distance acquired in childhood becomes a characteristic personal vulnerability of adults and persists for a long time, sometimes throughout life, and makes such people react more sharply to separation and social isolation than others.

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